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ISLOM KARIMOV NOMIDAGI TOSHKENT DAVLAT TEXNIKA UNIVERSITETI OLMALIQ FILIALI

«KIMYO SANOATINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI»

*Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya
2024 y. 1-2 ~~oktabr~~ noyabr, Olmaliq, Q'zbekiston*

Obmaliq 2024 y.

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DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY FOR THE COMPLEX PROCESSING OF MAN-MADE WASTE BASED ON INNOVATIVE METALLURGICAL PROCESSES

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In the context of modern industrial development, one of the urgent tasks is the processing of man-made waste generated during the production process. Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine JSC (Almalyk MMC) faces this problem, producing more than 30 million tons of waste annually. This waste contains valuable components such as iron, silicon and precious metals, but today the technologies for their processing are either absent or ineffective [1, p.19]. This study is aimed at developing a comprehensive waste processing technology that will not only extract valuable resources, but also solve important environmental problems. The complexity of processing man-made waste is due to their diverse chemical composition and high level of pollution. Waste from the beneficiation plants of Almalyk MMC JSC contains 30-35% of iron compounds, 25-30% silicon, 0.2 g / t gold and 1 g / t silver. Of course, the efficiency of extracting these components can significantly affect the economy of the enterprise and the ecosystem of the region [2, p.23]. At present, there is a need for innovative technologies that could ensure the efficient extraction of essential components from waste.

The main objective of the study is to develop a waste-free technology for the complex processing of technogenic waste with the possibility of extracting iron, silicon dioxide and precious metals [3, p.306]. The objectives of the study include:

1. Study of the chemical composition of waste and assessment of its recyclability.
2. Development of metallurgical processes that allow for the efficient extraction of valuable components.
3. Carrying out technical and economic calculations to assess the feasibility of the technology.
4. Testing the technology on a semi-industrial scale and preparing regulations for its implementation.

The development of a technology for the complex processing of waste will be based on modern scientific achievements in the field of metallurgy and chemistry. It is expected that a theoretical basis for the extraction processes will be created, which will improve the level of scientific knowledge in this area. The results obtained will be comparable with international studies conducted in countries with developed metallurgy, such as Chile and Canada. This will make it possible not only to improve existing technologies, but also to create new methodologies for waste processing [4, p.15].

The recycling technology will include combined metallurgical processes that will ensure a high degree of extraction of valuable components. The following stages will be developed within the framework of the study:

- Waste preparation: primary processing to isolate and classify components.
- Iron extraction: use of enrichment and smelting methods to extract iron and its compounds.
- Silicon dioxide production: application of modern chemical processing methods to extract silicon from waste.
- Precious metal extraction: use of hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical methods to extract gold and silver.

These processes will be analyzed and optimized to achieve maximum efficiency and minimize negative impact on the environment.

The implementation of this study will significantly increase the production of iron, silicon dioxide and precious metals. This will create new jobs, which, in turn, will contribute to the economic growth of the region and improve the standard of living of the population. The study will not only help reduce the amount of man-made waste, but also improve the environmental situation, which will be an important step towards sustainable development. In addition, the production of silicon dioxide will create a raw material base of more than 1 million tons for the chemical and light industries of Uzbekistan, which will significantly reduce dependence on imports.

The technology developed within the framework of the study has great potential for commercialization. It can be adapted both for the domestic market and for export to other countries facing similar waste disposal problems. Commercial implementation of the technology includes the production of various products based on extracted resources, such as iron and silicon compounds. High demand for these products entails the possibility of entering international markets and improving the competitiveness of Almalyk MMC JSC.

The main difference between the developed technology for complex waste processing of Almalyk MMC JSC and existing analogues is the integration of combined metallurgical processes aimed at maximum extraction of valuable components from the complex chemical composition of man-made waste, with minimal negative impact on the environment.

The developed technology for the integrated processing of waste by Almalyk MMC JSC is an innovative solution that not only meets modern requirements in the field of environmental sustainability, but also uses resources efficiently. The integration of various metallurgical processes, consideration of the complex chemical composition of waste and focus on waste-free technologies make this development unique in its kind and promising for implementation in industry. Thus, the study on the development of a technology for the integrated processing of man-made waste by Almalyk MMC JSC is an important step in solving the environmental and economic problems faced by the metallurgical industry of Uzbekistan. An innovative approach to waste processing will not only allow extracting valuable resources, but will also create a new raw material base for the chemical and light industries. The results of the study can become the basis for further research and development in the field of processing man-made waste, contributing to sustainable development not only in Uzbekistan, but also in other countries facing similar challenges.

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